

Development of Production Protocols for Local Sesame Varieties in a Tropical Agro-Ecological Setting

Vilma U. Atalin¹, Samuel R. Simon², Jonathan S. Balog³, John Paolo N. Faustino⁴

Department of Research and Development, Isabela State University, Cabagan, Isabela, 3328, Philippines^{1,2,3,4}

✉ vilma.atalin@isu.edu.ph

RESEARCH ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: September 26, 2025 Reviewed: November 22, 2025 Accepted: December 15, 2025 Published: December 29, 2025</p> <p> Copyright © 2025 by the Author(s). This open-access article is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>	<p>Sesame (<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.) is an ancient oilseed crop valued worldwide for its high-quality edible oil and protein. In the Philippines, sesame remains a minor crop compared to staples like rice and corn, despite its potential to enhance farmer livelihoods and nutrition. Expanding local sesame production could reduce dependence on imports, diversify income sources, and provide healthier oil alternatives for consumers. Productivity, however, is constrained by limited adoption of improved agronomic practices and a lack of varietal evaluation under local conditions. Addressing these challenges through research on fertilizer management and varietal performance across seasonal environments is essential to unlock sesame's potential as a profitable and sustainable crop. This study assessed sesame growth and yield under varying fertilizer treatments across wet and dry seasons (2022–2023). Results showed that the FT2 treatment (60-60-60 NPK/ha) + 10 bags organic fertilizer/ha) consistently produced the highest seed yield in both seasons (352.58 kg/ha in wet; 200.67 kg/ha in dry), along with superior capsule and seed counts. Among the tested varieties, black sesame (V2) outperformed brown sesame (V1), recording a significantly higher mean seed yield (321 kg/ha vs. 281 kg/ha). Although fertilizer rates did not significantly affect plant height, brown sesame produced taller plants. Findings highlight the benefits of organic fertilizer supplementation and the profitability of black</p>

sesame. Beyond supporting SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), this research demonstrates practical strategies for resilient cropping systems, reduced reliance on imports, and sustainable farmer incomes in the Philippines.

Keywords: *local sesame varieties, production protocols, inorganic fertilizer, organic fertilizer, tropical agro-ecological setting*

Introduction

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum L.*) is among the oldest oilseed crops in the world. In the Philippines, its production remains marginal. The Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) reported a 6.3% decline in sesame seed output in 2019 compared to 2018. By 2024, only five regions (Region I, IV-B, VI, VII, and XII) reported sesame production, totaling just 7.30 metric tons nationwide (PSA, 2020; PSA, 2024). Limited output has forced the country to rely heavily on imports. The Philippines now ranks 31st globally in sesame consumption (Tridge, 2024). These figures highlight the growing demand for sesame in health-oriented food markets and the persistent gap in local production capacity.

Although sesame is well-adapted to tropical and semitropical climates, it has not reached the same prominence in the Philippines as staple crops such as rice (*Oryza sativa L.*), corn (*Zea mays L.*), and coconut (*Cocos nucifera L.*). Sesame offers several benefits: its seeds are rich in protein, minerals, and antioxidants. Its deep root system improves soil structure and moisture retention. Its low water needs make it fit for drought-prone areas (Langham et al., 2008; FAO, 2021). These traits make sesame promising for sustainable agriculture and income diversification, especially in tropical agro-ecological setting like Cagayan Valley, where it is underutilized.

A notable research gap exists regarding systematic evaluations of sesame adaptability and yield performance in local conditions, especially in Region II (Cagayan Valley). Evidence is also limited on how varying fertilizer rates affect the productivity of local sesame varieties, including brown and black types. The lack of such data hinders the optimization of production practices and keeps the country reliant on imports.

This study aimed to evaluate the adaptability, phenotypic traits, and yield of selected sesame varieties in Cabagan, Isabela. It examined the impact of different organic fertilizer rates, based on soil analysis recommendations. Addressing this gap would inform strategies to expand sesame cultivation, improve farmer profitability, and support national goals for food security and sustainable agriculture.

The study used a theoretical framework that highlights crop adaptability and resource-use efficiency. The framework suggests matching crop traits (variety) with input management (fertilizer), while considering environmental factors (season, soil type), can boost productivity and resilience. It supports evaluating sesame as a diversification crop in Philippine agriculture. The research also aligns with broader higher education institutions' efforts, such as the KIST Model for agro-industrial innovation (Quebral Jr. & Barcellano, 2024), which emphasized integrating research and technology into crop development.

Methods

Research Design

Brown and black sesame seeds were chosen in this study because of their stronger flavor, greater nutritional value, and cultural authenticity (The Cooking Facts, 2024).

The study used a two-factor Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. This design evaluated sesame (*Sesamum indicum L.*) under different fertilizer treatments and varietal differences. Factor A had five fertilizer treatments, ranging from the recommended rate (60-60-60 NPK/ha) to combinations with various levels of organic fertilizer. Factor B included two sesame varieties: brown (V1) and black (V2). This design controlled experimental error and allowed treatment effects to be compared statistically across replications.

Figure 1. *The Sesame Field Experimental Area*

Participants/Respondents

As an agronomic field experiment, the study's subjects were the sesame plants themselves, representing the two tested varieties. The research team from the R&D Central Experiment Station acted as implementers and observers.

Site of the Study

The experiment took place at the R&D Central Experiment Station in Cabagan, Isabela, Philippines. The site has sandy loam soil with a pH of 6.5, medium organic matter, and low available nitrogen and phosphorus, conditions suitable for sesame cultivation. The study was conducted across two contrasting seasonal environments to examine the effects of climate on crop performance.

During the wet season (June–September 2022), the area received about 1,200 mm of rainfall. Mean temperatures ranged from 27 to 30 °C, and relative humidity averaged 80–85%. In contrast, the dry season (January–April 2023) had less than 200 mm of rainfall, mean temperatures of 29–32 °C, and 65–70% relative humidity. Weather data for both seasons came from the nearest Agrometeorological Station (Agro-Met) at DA-Cagayan Valley Research Center (CVRC) in San Felipe, City of Ilagan, Isabela.

Research Instruments

The main research instruments were field plots measuring 2.8 m by 5 m. Each plot had a spacing of 1.0 m between plots and blocks. Fertilizer treatments included both inorganic (NPK) and campus-made organic input. Laboratory analysis showed the vermicompost had about 1.5% nitrogen (N), 1.2% phosphorus pentoxide (P₂O₅), and 1.0% potassium oxide (K₂O), with a pH of 7.2. All treatments received uniform application, supporting reliable comparisons with inorganic fertilizer rates.

Data Collection Procedure

A systematic data-collection process was used. Land preparation included one plowing and two harrowing at one-week intervals to remove weeds and improve soil tilth. Seeds were sown at the correct spacing, then thinned after one week to keep 2–3 vigorous plants per hill. Fertilizer was applied in two split doses: 50% before planting and 50% as side-dressing at 30 days. Irrigation occurred twice, once after planting (if needed) and once at the pre-flowering stage. Sesame's high C: N ratio kept weed pressure low, so no herbicides were used. Pest and disease pressure were low, so no insecticides or fungicides were needed. Field observations noted minor leaf spot and some insect feeding, but neither required chemical control. Harvesting began once 70–80% of the leaves turned yellow. Plants were cut at the base, tied in bundles, and sun-dried for 3–5 days. Seeds were manually threshed, cleaned, and stored in airtight containers at room temperature to prevent mold.

Analysis of Data

Data were analyzed using Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research (STAR) software, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) determined the differences among treatments. To compare treatment means, Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% significance was also used. This approach ensured rigorous evaluation of fertilizer and varietal effects.

Ethical Considerations

The study followed ethical standards in agricultural research. No humans or animals were used, so ethical risks were minimal. Using organic fertilizer promoted sustainability, and avoiding chemical pesticides and herbicides reduced ecological impact. Data integrity was ensured by following standardized procedures and reporting results transparently.

Results and Discussion

Wet Cropping Season 2022

Both sesame varieties (brown and black) emerged uniformly five days after planting (DAP). No significant difference was observed, indicating that seed vigor and establishment were comparable under wet-season conditions. This finding matches with Morris (2002) who claimed that sesame's rapid and uniform germination is evident when soil moisture is adequate.

Flowering

Black sesame flowered earlier (35 DAP) than brown sesame (45 DAP), but statistical analysis showed no significant difference. Early flowering in black sesame may indicate a shorter vegetative phase, enabling earlier allocation of resources to

reproductive growth. Langham et al. (2008) found that differences in flowering time among varieties can affect adaptability to seasonal conditions.

Maturity

Black sesame matured at 112 days after planting (DAP). Brown sesame matured later at 120 DAP. Again, differences were not statistically significant. Black sesame's earlier maturity aligns with its earlier flowering, suggesting a potential advantage in areas with shorter growing seasons or limited water. However, since the difference was not statistically significant, both varieties can be managed similarly in terms of harvest timing under wet-season conditions.

While differences in flowering and maturity between the two varieties were not statistically significant, the observed trend of earlier development in black sesame may have practical implications. Early flowering and maturity can reduce exposure to late-season rainfall, pests, or diseases, potentially enhancing harvest efficiency. These results underscore the importance of varietal selection in relation to seasonal conditions and support previous studies that recommend aligning crop phenology with local climate patterns to optimize yield and stability.

Plant Height at Harvest (cm)

The statistical analysis revealed that fertilizer levels did not significantly affect sesame plant height at harvest. This suggests that nutrient inputs, within the tested range, do not strongly influence vegetative growth. Similar findings have been reported in field trials where fertilizer application had little effect on sesame height, with yield parameters such as capsule number and seed weight being more responsive than plant stature (Madankar et al., 2025).

Table 1. Varietal Response in Plant Height to Different Fertilizer Rates at Harvest

Factor B Variety	Mean
V1 - Brown Sesame	168.25 ^a
V2 - Black Sesame	146.17 ^b
CV (b) = 14.81%	

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Varietal Differences in Plant Height

A significant difference was observed between the two sesame varieties. V1 (Brown Sesame) reached a mean height of 168.25 cm, while V2 (Black Sesame) averaged 146.17 cm. This demonstrates that V1 plants consistently grew taller than V2 plants. Previous studies confirmed that sesame varieties differ widely in plant architecture, with some cultivars reaching up to 180 cm in height under favorable conditions, while others remain shorter (Zehra et al., 2017).

Interaction Between Fertilizer and Variety

The interaction between fertilizer level and variety was not statistically significant. This indicates that the relative difference in plant height between V1 and V2 is consistent across fertilizer treatments. Thus, the taller growth habit of V1 is a varietal trait rather than a response to nutrient inputs (James et al., 2023).

Number of Seeds per Capsule

Based on Table 2, Fertilizer Treatment 2 produced the highest mean number of seeds per capsule (81 seeds), demonstrating a statistically significant improvement compared to the other treatments. This finding highlights the strong influence of fertilizer application on seed productivity.

Table 2. Effect of Fertilizer Rates on Seed Count per Capsule

Factor A (Fertilizer rate)	Mean
FT1 – RR (60-60-60 NPK)	55 ^b
FT2 – RR + 100% organic fertilizer (OF):10 bags/ha	81 ^a
FT3 – RR + 80% OF	61 ^b
FT4 – RR + 60% OF	60 ^b
FT5 – RR + 40% OF	54 ^b
CV (b) = 14.81%	

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Similarly, Table 2.1 shows that Variety V1 consistently outperformed Variety V2, with a significantly higher mean number of seeds per capsule. The coefficient of variation (CV) of 14.13% indicates moderate variability across the two varieties, suggesting that genetic differences play a substantial role in determining seed yield potential. While both fertilizer rate and variety exerted significant effects, their interaction was not statistically significant, suggesting that each variety's response to fertilizer application was relatively consistent across rates.

Table 2.1 Varietal Response to Fertilizer Rates on Seed Number per Capsule

Factor B Variety	Mean
V1 - Brown Sesame	66.56 ^a
V2 – Black Sesame	57.5 ^b
CV (b) = 14.13%	

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Earlier research showed that fertilizer inputs can enhance capsule development and seed set. Dollison and Dollison (2023) reported that organic fertilizer treatments increased capsule size and seed number in sesame. Similarly, Guda et al. (2024) found that liquid biofertilizers improved reproductive traits, including seed count per capsule. Varietal differences have also been documented. Bodaka et al. (2021) observed significant variation in capsule traits among sesame varieties, confirming that genotype plays a dominant role in determining seed number.

Seed Yield Kg/ha

The results presented in Table 3 reveal that Fertilizer Treatment 2 (FT2) achieved the highest mean seed yield of 352.58 kg/ha, which was significantly greater than that of Fertilizer Treatment 1 (FT1: 271.77 kg/ha). In contrast, the yields of FT1, FT3, FT4, and FT5 were not significantly different from one another, suggesting that adding organic fertilizer in these treatments did not provide a statistically significant advantage over the base recommendation (RR) alone. This finding indicates that while fertilizer

application is crucial, excessive or unbalanced inputs may not necessarily translate into higher yields.

Table 3. Effect of Fertilizer Rates on Average Seed Yield kg/ ha

Factor A (Fertilizer rate)	Mean
FT1 – RR (60-60-60 NPK)	271.77 ^b
FT2 – RR + 100% organic fertilizer (OF):10 bags/ha	352.58 ^a
FT3 – RR + 80% OF	296.02 ^b
FT4 - RR + 60% OF	303.28 ^b
FT5 – RR + 40% OF	282.42 ^b
CV (a) = 8.58 %	

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

The varietal response, as shown in Table 3.1, further highlights the importance of genetic factors. Variety V1 produced a mean of 281 seeds per capsule, whereas Variety V2 yielded a significantly higher mean of 321 seeds per capsule.

Correspondingly, V2 also demonstrated a higher mean seed yield compared to V1, underscoring the substantial influence of varietal selection on sesame productivity. Notably, the interaction between fertilizer rates and variety was not significant, implying that both varieties responded consistently to the applied fertilizer treatments.

Table 3.1. Varietal Response to Fertilizer Rates on Average Seed Yield kg/ha

Factor B Variety	Mean
V1 - Brown Sesame	281 ^b
V2 – Black Sesame	321 ^a
CV (b) = 8.47%	

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

These findings align with earlier studies. For instance, Ofosuhene et al. (2010) reported average sesame yields of 471.2 kg/ha under favorable conditions, suggesting that environmental factors, such as typhoons in the present trial, may have constrained yield potential. Similar research across Africa and Asia has demonstrated that optimal fertilizer management enhances sesame yield, but varietal differences remain a dominant factor in determining productivity.

Studies in Ethiopia and Bangladesh, for example, have shown that improved varieties, combined with balanced fertilizer application, can substantially increase seed yield. In contrast, excessive or poorly timed fertilizer inputs often fail to deliver additional benefits.

The significant yield advantage observed with Fertilizer Treatment 2 (FT2) indicates that optimized fertilizer regimes can substantially enhance farmers' productivity. Conversely, the absence of significant yield differences among FT1, FT3, FT4, and FT5 suggests that excessive or unbalanced fertilizer inputs do not confer additional benefits and may increase production costs. Efficient fertilizer use and the selection of high-yielding varieties such as V2, which consistently outperformed V1 in seed yield, are therefore recommended.

For policymakers, these results underscore the necessity of agricultural extension programs that disseminate best practices in fertilizer management and

varietal selection. Policies facilitating access to affordable fertilizers and certified high-yielding varieties could enhance national sesame production.

Additionally, given the impact of environmental factors such as typhoons on yield potential, support for climate-resilient farming strategies, including crop insurance schemes and disaster preparedness initiatives, is warranted. The pronounced varietal differences observed highlight the importance of ongoing breeding efforts to develop sesame varieties that combine high yield potential with resilience to environmental stresses.

For agribusiness stakeholders, input suppliers can refine fertilizer recommendations to emphasize regimes similar to FT2, while seed companies can promote high-yielding varieties such as V2. Increased sesame yields have downstream implications for agribusiness, including greater supply for oil extraction and food processing industries.

Dry Cropping Season 2022-2023

In terms of emergence timing, both Brown and Black Sesame varieties displayed no significant difference, with all entries germinating at five (5) days after planting (DAP). Regarding the days to flowering, no significant difference was found between the two varieties. Brown Sesame (V1) took 50 days to flower, while Black Sesame (V2) flowered 39 days after emergence (DAE). Based on the gathered data, Brown Sesame (V1) took 125 days to reach maturity, while Black Sesame (V2) matured in 100 days. No significant difference was observed between the two varieties.

Plant Height at Harvest (cm)

In Table 4, the mean plant height varied across fertilizer rates. FT2 achieved the highest mean plant height at 173.72 cm, while FT1 achieved the shortest mean plant height among all treatments. A trend emerged indicating an increase in plant height with a higher percentage of organic fertilizer in combination with the recommended inorganic fertilizer.

Hence, based on the results, ANOVA revealed that the different rates of organic fertilizer significantly affect plant height at harvest.

Table 4. Varietal Response in Plant Height to Different Fertilizer Rates at Harvest

Factor A (Fertilizer rate)	Mean
FT1 – RR (60-60-60 NPK)	134.02 ^c
FT2 – RR + 100% organic fertilizer (OF):10 bags/ha	173.72 ^a
FT3 – RR + 80% OF	160.12 ^{ab}
FT4 - RR + 60% OF	152.55 ^{abc}
FT5 – RR + 40% OF	137.47 ^{bc}
CV (a) = 11.72%	

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different

The two varieties (Brown and Black Sesame) did not have a statistically significant effect on plant height, although the result is close to significance, indicating a potential trend.

Table 4.1. Interaction Effects of Fertilizer Rates and Sesame Varieties on Average Plant Height at Harvest (cm)

Variety	Fertilizer Rates				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
V1-Brown Sesame	154.8	188.4	166.73	159.56	147.03
V2- Black Sesame	113.23	159.03	153.50	145.53	127.90

Table 4.1 shows the interaction between fertilizer rates and sesame varieties on average plant height at harvest. For the brown sesame variety (V1), the tallest plants were observed under FT2 (188.4 cm), while the shortest plants occurred under FT5 (147.03 cm). Similarly, for the black sesame variety (V2), the highest mean plant height was recorded under FT2 (159.03 cm), whereas the lowest was under FT1 (113.23 cm). Although these numerical differences suggest that FT2 promoted greater vegetative growth in both varieties, statistical analysis revealed that the interaction between fertilizer levels and sesame varieties was not significant. This indicates that both varieties responded similarly to the applied fertilizer treatments.

The increase in plant height under FT2 supports earlier findings that combining inorganic and organic fertilizers enhances sesame growth (Braganza, 2023; Tehulie, Nuru, 2019). However, consistent with Salame et al. (2020), excessive organic inputs beyond optimal levels did not yield significant gains, mirroring the lack of statistical differences observed in this study.

Number of Seeds per Capsule

A consistent trend emerged where FT2 yielded the highest mean number of seeds per capsule, with 77. Comparable results were observed for FT3 at 61, FT4 at 57, FT5 at 53, and the lowest but still comparable FT1 at 50.

Based on the ANOVA results, the sesame varieties (Brown and Black) are not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Still, the p-value is close to significance (p-value = 0.0565), suggesting a potential trend that the variety may influence the number of seeds per capsule. Fertilizer application significantly influenced seed number per capsule, with both varieties producing the highest counts under FT2. Still, the interaction between fertilizer level and variety was not significant, indicating similar varietal responses to fertilization.

Seed Yield kg/ha

The highest seed yield per hectare was achieved with the FT2 treatment, which included RR + 100% Organic Fertilizer, yielding 200.67 kg/ha. The other treatments showed comparable results. FT3 treatment yielded 179.43 kg/ha, FT1 171.98 kg/ha, FT4 166.05 kg/ha, and FT5 164.15 kg/ha, respectively. ANOVA results showed that the effect of variety is not significant (p = 0.6957). The high coefficient of variation (CV-a=8.67% and CV-b=20.33%) indicates considerable yield variability, which can be attributed to extreme drought stress experienced during dry-season planting.

Both sesame varieties achieved their highest yields under FT2, with brown sesame (V1) producing 192.0 kg/ha and black sesame (V2) 209.3 kg/ha. Overall, V2 yielded more than V1 across all fertilizer treatments. For V1, yields declined as the proportion of organic fertilizer decreased from FT2 to FT5, while for V2, FT1 produced the third-highest yield. Statistical analysis showed that fertilizer level significantly

influenced yield, but the interaction between fertilizer level and variety was not significant ($p = 0.9101$), indicating that fertilizer effects were consistent across varieties.

Costs and Return Analyses

Table 5. Cost and Return Analysis of Black Sesame During Wet Season 2022

Particulars	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
<i>I. Inputs</i>					
A. Labor Cost	24,000.00	25,680.00	25,260.00	24,840.00	24,420.00
B. Supplies and Materials	16,461.00	18,461.00	18,061.00	17,661.00	17,261.00
Total Production Cost	40,461.00	44,141.00	43,321.00	42,501.00	41,681.00
<i>II. Output</i>					
Yield Kg/hectare	292.9	350.5	329.3	325.8	307.0
Gross Income (P380/kg)	111,302.00	133,190.00	125,134.00	123,804.00	116,660.00
<i>III. Income Analysis</i>					
Net Income	70,841.00	89,049.00	81,813.00	81,303.00	74,979.00
ROI (%)	175.10	201.70	188.85	191.30	179.89

Black sesame demonstrated strong profitability during the wet season, with all treatments yielding positive net incomes and ROI values exceeding 175.10%. Treatment 2 achieved the highest yield and ROI (201.7%), indicating efficient resource utilization despite higher production costs. Other treatments yielded moderate returns, suggesting that profitability is robust across input levels but maximized under optimal fertilizer management.

These findings support earlier reports that sesame responds positively to balanced nutrient inputs, with diminishing returns beyond optimal rates (Langham et al., 2008).

Table 6. Cost and Return Analysis of Brown Sesame During Wet Season 2022

Particulars	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
<i>I. Inputs</i>					
A. Labor Cost	24,000.00	25,680.00	25,260.00	24,840.00	24,420.00
B. Supplies and Materials	16,101.00	18,101.00	17,701.00	17,301.00	16,901.00
Total Production Cost	40,101.00	43,781.00	42,961.00	42,141.00	41,321.00
<i>II. Output</i>					
Yield Kg/hectare	250.6	354.6	262.7	280.7	257.9
Gross Income (P380/kg)	65,156.00	92,196.00	68,302.00	72,982.00	67,054.00
<i>III. Income Analysis</i>					
Net Income	25,055.00	48,415.00	25,341.00	30,841.00	25,733.00
ROI (%)	62.5	110.6	59.0	73.2	62.3

Brown sesame yield and profitability varied across fertilizer treatments during the wet season. Treatment 2 achieved the highest yield (354.6 kg/ha) and ROI (110.6%), indicating efficient resource utilization despite higher input costs. Other treatments produced positive net incomes but with lower efficiency, suggesting diminishing returns at higher input levels. These findings align with reports that moderate fertilizer application optimizes sesame productivity in tropical environments (FAO, 2021).

Table 7. Cost and Return Analysis of Black Sesame During Dry Season 2023

Particulars	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
<i>I. Inputs</i>					
A. Labor Cost	25,680.00	27,360.00	26,940.00	26,520.00	26,100.00
B. Supplies and Materials	16,461.00	18,461.00	18,061.00	17,661.00	17,261.00
Total Production Cost	42,141.00	45,821.00	45,001.00	44,181.00	43,361.00
<i>II. Output</i>					
Yield Kg/hectare	181.2	209.3	184.7	160.3	159.9
Gross Income (P380/kg)	68,856.00	79,534.00	70,186.00	60,914.00	60,762.00
<i>III. Income Analysis</i>					
Net Income	26,715.00	33,713.00	25,185.00	16,733.00	17,401.00
ROI (%)	63.4	73.6	56.0	37.9	40.1

Dry season production of black sesame yielded lower returns compared to wet season trials, reflecting the influence of climatic constraints on crop performance. Treatment 2 achieved the highest yield (209.3 kg/ha) and ROI (73.6%), indicating efficient resource utilization despite higher input costs. Other treatments produced modest net incomes, with ROI declining sharply under lower-yield conditions.

Table 8. Cost and Return Analysis of Brown Sesame During Dry Season 2023

Particulars	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
<i>I. Inputs</i>					
A. Labor Cost	25,680.00	27,360.00	26,940.00	26,520.00	26,100.00
B. Supplies and Materials	16,101.00	18,101.00	17,701.00	17,301.00	16,901.00
Total Production Cost	41,781.00	45,461.00	44,641.00	43,821.00	43,001.00
<i>II. Output</i>					
Yield Kg/hectare	162.7	192.0	174.2	171.8	168.4
Gross Income (P380/kg)	42,302.00	49,920.00	45,292.00	44,668.00	43,784.00
<i>III. Income Analysis</i>					
Net Income	521.00	4,459.00	651.00	847.00	783.00
ROI (%)	1.25	9.81	1.46	1.93	1.82

Brown sesame exhibited weak profitability during the dry season, with net incomes close to break-even and ROI values below 10% across treatments. Although Treatment 2 achieved the highest yield (192 kg/ha) and ROI (9.81%), returns were insufficient to justify production costs. These results contrast sharply with wet-season trials and black sesame performance, underscoring brown sesame's limited adaptability to dry-season conditions.

For farmers, the significant yield advantage of Fertilizer Treatment 2 (FT2) demonstrates that adopting optimized fertilizer regimes can substantially increase productivity. At the same time, the lack of significant yield differences among FT1, FT3, FT4, and FT5 suggests that excessive or unbalanced fertilizer inputs do not provide additional benefits and may unnecessarily increase production costs. Farmers are therefore encouraged to prioritize efficient fertilizer use and select high-yielding varieties such as V2, which consistently outperformed V1 in seed yield.

Policymakers, these results highlight the need for agricultural extension programs that disseminate best practices in fertilizer management and varietal selection. Policies that ensure access to affordable fertilizers and certified high-yielding varieties could enhance national sesame production. Furthermore, given that environmental factors, such as typhoons, can constrain yield potential, policymakers should support climate-resilient farming strategies, including crop insurance schemes and disaster preparedness initiatives.

Researchers and breeders have observed pronounced varietal differences, underscoring the importance of continued breeding efforts to develop sesame varieties that combine high yield potential with resilience to environmental stress.

Agribusiness stakeholders, input suppliers can refine fertilizer recommendations to emphasize regimes similar to FT2, while seed companies can promote high-yielding varieties such as V2. Increased sesame yields have downstream implications for agribusiness, including greater supply for oil extraction and food processing industries.

Conclusion and Future Works

The study demonstrated that applying FT2-RR (60-60-60 NPK) combined with 100% organic fertilizer consistently enhanced sesame performance across both wet and dry seasons, resulting in improved seed yield, plant height, capsule number, and seed count. Black sesame achieved a higher return on investment in both seasons, underscoring its economic advantage for farmers. Although sesame is drought-tolerant, both black and brown varieties performed better under wet season conditions, confirming that greater moisture availability supports higher yields and aligning with previous findings that sesame responds positively to increased water supply.

Farmers are encouraged to adopt FT2-RR with organic fertilizer supplementation to maximize productivity and prioritize black sesame cultivation, particularly during the wet season, while considering site-specific conditions to minimize risks such as lodging. Policymakers and extension services should promote the use of organic fertilizers through training and subsidy programs, support the breeding and dissemination of climate-adapted sesame varieties, and strengthen extension initiatives to guide season-specific planting strategies.

Future research may investigate alternative fertilizer combinations, evaluate seasonal planting strategies across diverse agro-ecological zones, explore plant growth regulation to optimize height and reduce lodging, and conduct economic analyses of sesame value chains to inform farmer decision-making and policy interventions.

References

- [1] Ali, M. S., Zahid, Z., Siddike, N., Bappi, M. Z. H., Payel, N. A., Islam, T., Rahman, M. J., & Mohsin, G. (2023). Effect of different levels of organic fertilizer on growth, yield, and economic benefits of radish (*Raphanus sativus* L.). *Journal of Science Technology and Environment Informatics*, 30, 2533–2540. <https://doi.org/10.18801/jbar.300223.306>
- [2] Bedigian, D. (2004). History and lore of sesame in Southwest Asia. *Economic Botany*, 58(3), 330–353. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4256831>
- [3] Bedigian, D., & van der Maesen, L. J. G. (2003). *Status and importance of the oilseed sesame in Africa*. Paper presented at the PROTA Conference, Kenya, September 23–25, 2002.
- [4] Bodaka, V. P., Singh, V., & Singh, A. K. (2021). Effect of plant population and varieties on growth and yield of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 10(12), 645–648. <https://www.thepharmajournal.com/archives/?year=2021&vol=10&issue=12&ArticleId=9379>
- [5] Braganza, J. (2023). Integrated nutrient management practices for sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) under Philippine conditions. *Philippine Journal of Crop Science*, 48(2), 115–124.
- [6] Dollison, M. D., & Dollison, B. B. (2023). Agronomic performance of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) under different fertilizer management. *Biosaintifika: Journal of Biology & Biology Education*, 15(3), 378–385. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/ec5f/3e5a0039c90cc1c338aa6ff1e0646d546c4e.pdf>
- [7] Guda, T., Jyothi, K. N., Rani, B. S., Kumari, P. L., & Chandrika, V. (2024). Influence of liquid biofertilizers on growth and yield of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *International Journal of Plant & Soil Science*, 36(10), 534–540. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijpss/2024/v36i105104>
- [8] Langham, D. R. (2008). *Growth and development of sesame* (Report). Sesaco Corporation. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330666828_SESAME_GROWER_GUIDE
- [9] Madankar, P., Bisen, J. S., Patle, A., & Turkar, D. (2025). Impact of organic and bio fertilizers on yield of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *International Journal of Research in Agronomy*, 8(11), 12-15. <https://doi.org/10.33545/2618060X.2025.v8.i11a.4134>
- [10] Morris, J. B. (2002). Food, industrial, nutraceutical, and pharmaceutical uses of sesame genetic resources. In J. Janick & A. Whipkey (Eds.), *Trends in new crops and new uses* (pp. 153–156). ASHS Press.

- [11] Ofosuhene Sintim, H., & Yeboah-Badu, V. I. (2010). Evaluation of sesame (*Sesamum indicum*) production in Ghana. *Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, 6(3), 653–662. <https://m.elewa.org/JAPS/2010/6.3/2.pdf>
- [12] Olusola, O. J., Adejoro, S. A., Aiyelari, O. P., & Akinbuwa, O. (2023). Effects of fertilizer application on growth, yield, and nutritional quality of black sesame (*Sesamum radiatum* Schum). *Journal of Plant Sciences*, 11(3), 80–85. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jps.20231103.16>
- [13] Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA). (2020). *Major crops statistics of the Philippines*.
- [14] Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA). (2024). *Regional agricultural production report*.
- [15] Quebral, B. A., Jr., & Barcellano, E. V. (2024). Establishment of an integrated agro-industrial special economic zone on Knowledge, Innovation, Science and Technology (KIST) model in ISU Cabagan Campus. *Linker Journal of Emerging Research in Agriculture, Fisheries and Forestry*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.65141/jeraff.v4i1.n3>
- [16] Salame, R., Mishra, U. S., Mohbe, S., Subhash, Dotaniya, C. K., Pahade, V., Doutaniya, R. K., & Wagadre, D. (2020). Influence of growth and yield attributes of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) by Sulphur and Phosphorus fertilizer combinations under rainfed condition. *Indian Journal of Pure and Applied Biosciences*, 8(4), 115–124. <https://doi.org/10.18782/2582-2845.8200>
- [17] The Cooking Facts. (2024). *Which sesame seeds are better: Black or white?* <https://thecookingfacts.com/which-sesame-seeds-are-better-black-or-white/>
- [18] Zehra, S., Koaser, R., Ahmad, Z., Naz, N., Atta, M., Satti, S., Shahbaz, M., & Sarwar. (2017). Screening of different varieties of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) for growth, yield and oil response under warm climatic conditions. *SYLWAN*, 161(6), 288-302. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327465887>
- [19] Zewdie, T., & Tehulie, N. S. (2019). Review on effects of plant densities and nitrogen fertilization on sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) yield and yield components. *International Journal of Research in Agronomy*, 2(1), 42–47. <https://doi.org/10.33545/2618060X.2019.v2.i1a.66>

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the guidance and blessings of our Lord Jesus Christ throughout the conduct of this study. Sincere appreciation is extended to the Department of Research and Development of Isabela State University, Cabagan Campus, for providing research funding and technical assistance. The valuable contributions of the research staff, who generously shared their time and expertise during the experimental trials, are deeply appreciated.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the conduct and publication of this study. All procedures were carried out independently, and no financial or personal relationships influenced the results or conclusions presented.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Declaration Statement

AI tools such as ChatGPT were used only for language editing and manuscript organization. All content was thoroughly reviewed, verified, and edited by the authors to ensure accuracy and integrity.